

RAwR: Role-Aware Rewiring via Approximate Equitable Partition

ICML '26 Rebuttal

This markdown has been produced to give the reviewers the opportunity of getting more detailed answers to their questions, outside the limitations of the 5000 characters in OpenReview. Additional experiments are collected in the Appendix 4.2.2.

1 Official Review of Submission12905 by Reviewer Buhs

1.1 Summary:

This paper presents a principled approach to add virtual nodes (VNs) to a graph for GNN-based node classification. The proposed VNs are added based on role-based structure, that is, based on the similarities between local structural patterns for each node. VNs facilitate connections between nodes that may be more relevant than the original graph implies, and this approach assumes that nodes with similar structural roles may benefit from sharing information rather than relying solely on their distances in the graph.

1.2 Strengths And Weaknesses:

This work is very clean and principled. It seems clear that you have a good understanding of what your method does and why it works. The experimental results too include accessible discussions that address the reasons why your method is expected to perform well, which are empirically supported. [Answer: We sincerely thank the Reviewer for the very positive assessment of our work, and especially for recognizing its novelty, clarity, and principled nature. We are also grateful for the detailed and thoughtful feedback useful even for future research directions. Regarding the concerns and clarifications requested, below we address each point in detail.] In terms of changes to the manuscript, besides minor edits and one primary recommendation, I have no particular suggestions. For future consideration, you might want to look into extending this work looking into other graph structural properties as bases for defining VN groups. For example, nodes with similar spectral properties (such as eigenvector centrality) may be more likely to belong to the same class for certain applications, perhaps for identifying influential individuals in a social network based on their effects over the entire graph.

[Answer: We thank the reviewer for this insightful suggestion. In fact, one of the advantages of Equitable Partition is that, as stated in [1] and [2], which are cited in our paper, various centrality measures, such as eigenvector centrality, are shared between the quotient graph and the original graph: this means that all nodes connected to a RAwR virtual node have indeed the same (if $\varepsilon = 0$) or similar (if $\varepsilon \neq 0$) eigenvector centrality. We agree that making this connection more explicit

would strengthen the manuscript, and we will add a short discussion to clarify this.]

[Additional References: [1] Squillace, G., Tribastone, M., Tschaikowski, M., and Vandin, A. Efficient network embedding by approximate equitable partitions. In Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining (ICDM), 2024

[2] Scholkemper, M. and Schaub, M. T. An optimization-based approach to node role discovery in networks: Approximating equitable partitions. In Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), 2023.]

1.3 Key Questions For Authors:

1.3.1 Main comments:

You need to say why VNs connecting nodes of the same role is a good choice. I understand role-based structure is well established, and your empirical results demonstrate this as being suitable for the datasets in your work, but this is not the same as showing why node structural roles are principled. For example, in lines 376-377, column 1: "... rather than explicit message passing among role representatives", this seems to support the inferiority of MN, as it is not necessarily helpful to add 3-hop connections between nodes associated with different roles. It appears to be more helpful to instead maintain existing connections between nodes of different roles. This further emphasizes the importance of justifying why role-based structure is a good choice for VNs. [Answer: We thank the reviewer for the observation. The choice of using structural roles to define VNs is motivated by the fact that nodes with similar structural roles have similar functions in the graph from a dynamical point of view (many works cited in [1] and [2] delve deeper into this topic) and therefore may benefit from sharing information. On the matter on how this type of rewiring is actually helpful for the task of node classification, we highlight that we already cited some works ([3–5]) in the Introduction to support the usefulness of leveraging structural roles, both when node labels are known to be aligned with them or not. Furthermore, in Section 4 and in the Appendix A, B and C, we show both formally and empirically how the accuracy performances obtained with RAwR are correlated to the SRL metric on both synthetic and real-world datasets.

[1] Squillace, G., Tribastone, M., Tschaikowski, M., and Vandin, A. Efficient network embedding by approximate equitable partitions. In Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining (ICDM), 2024

[2] Scholkemper, M. and Schaub, M. T. An optimization-based approach to node role discovery in networks: Approximating equitable partitions. In Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), 2023.

[3] Henderson, K., Gallagher, B., Eliassi-Rad, T., Tong, H., Basu, S., Akoglu, L., Koutra, D., Faloutsos, C., and Li, L. Rolx: structural role extraction & mining in large graphs. In Proceedings of the 18th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, KDD '12, pp. 1231–1239, New York, NY, USA, 2012. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 9781450314626. doi: 10.1145/2339530.2339723.

[4] Cui, H., Lu, Z., Li, P., and Yang, C. On positional and structural node features for graph neural networks on non-attributed graphs. In Proceedings of the 31st ACM International Conference on Information & Knowledge Management, CIKM '22, pp. 3898–3902, New York, NY, USA, 2022. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 9781450392365. doi: 10.1145/3511808.3557661.

[5] Peel, L. Active discovery of network roles for predicting the classes of network nodes. *Journal of Complex Networks*, 3(3):431–449, 11 2014. ISSN 20511310. doi: 10.1093/comnet/cnu043.

[6] Park, H. and Neville, J. Role equivalence attention for label propagation in graph neural networks.

In Lauw, H. W., Wong, R. C.-W., Ntoulas, A., Lim, E.-P., Ng, S.-K., and Pan, S. J. (eds.), *Advances in Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, pp. 555–567, Cham, 2020. Springer International Publishing. ISBN 978-3-030-47436-2.]

Lines 143-144, column 1: ”obtaining accuracy improvements of up to +12%” On what? The percentage increase seems meaningless without context. [Answer: We will revise this sentence to make it clearer. The reported improvement refers to the difference of node classification accuracy on RAwR-rewired graphs with respect to the corresponding non-rewired graphs, using the same backbone architecture (GCN, GAT, or GIN). To give an example, RepNodes with GCN on the Cornell dataset with no features achieves an accuracy of 55.56%, while GCN on the original graph achieves an accuracy of 44.44%, which corresponds to a +11.12% improvement.]

Line 239, column 1: Perhaps you ought to explain when and why your assumption regarding the student on the original graph is reasonable. Is this strict? [Answer: We clarify that this assumption is not a strict requirement of RAwR, but an analytical abstraction which is reasonable when the label signal is sufficiently smooth with respect to the graph, so that it can be approximated by a polynomial graph filter. This is a standard viewpoint in graph signal processing and in spectral GNN analysis [7–10], and is consistent with the well-known Laplacian-smoothing behavior of GCN-type models [11,12]. We also add the same reasoning goes for the teacher model, for which we assume that it retrieves the true labels by leveraging the RAwR-rewired graph as proxy of the true latent graph. The idea of observed graphs being approximations of a richer latent structure is common in graph structure learning [13].]

[Additional References: [7] Ortega, Antonio, Pascal Frossard, Jelena Kovačević, José M. F. Moura, and Pierre Vandergheynst. “Graph Signal Processing: Overview, Challenges, and Applications.” *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 106, no. 5, 2018, pp. 808–828.

[8] Defferrard, Michaël, Xavier Bresson, and Pierre Vandergheynst. “Convolutional Neural Networks on Graphs with Fast Localized Spectral Filtering.” *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 29, 2016, pp. 3844–3852.

[9] Kipf, Thomas N., and Max Welling. “Semi-Supervised Classification with Graph Convolutional Networks.” *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2017.

[10] Wu, Felix, Tianyi Zhang, Amauri Holanda de Souza, Christopher Fifty, Tao Yu, and Kilian Q. Weinberger. “Simplifying Graph Convolutional Networks.” *Proceedings of the 36th International Conference on Machine Learning*, vol. 97, PMLR, 2019, pp. 6861–6871.

[11] Li, Qimai, Zhichao Han, and Xiao-Ming Wu. “Deeper Insights into Graph Convolutional Networks for Semi-Supervised Learning.” *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 32, no. 1, 2018.

[12] NT, Hoang, and Takanori Maehara. “Revisiting Graph Neural Networks: All We Have Is Low-Pass Filters.” *arXiv*, 2019, arXiv:1905.09550.

[13] Franceschi, Luca, Mathias Niepert, Massimiliano Pontil, and Xiao He. “Learning Discrete Structures for Graph Neural Networks.” *Proceedings of the 36th International Conference on Machine Learning*, vol. 97, PMLR, 2019, pp. 1972–1982.]

Lines 316-317, column 2: ”... structural rewiring remains complementary even for more expressive message passing schemes” Perhaps this implies that certain heterophilic graphs, we require multiple hops to aggregate sufficient information? GAT learns attention weights for direct links between node pairs, but it may be outperformed by RepNodes or RepEdges if multiple hops are required to characterize node classes. I think this finding is interesting, and the insights might lead to useful assessments of these graphs as heterophilic benchmarks. [Answer: This is indeed what we expected from GAT+RAwR on heterophilic graphs, where links to virtual nodes get larger attention weights, especially where we use only the topology of the graph, without node features. Nonetheless, we

thank the reviewer for the suggestion of using RAwR+Attention to assess heterophilic benchmarks: this is a very precious insight.] In the same vein, in line 361, column 1: "... highlighting the limitations of introducing a single global hub that indiscriminately aggregates information" What are the limitations exactly? I suspect that this aligns with your discussion on GATs and GINs, where optimizing a one-hop connection may be insufficient, regardless of how expressive your GNN architecture is. Conversely, solely adding connections is not enough either, as MN is consistently outperformed by RepNodes and RepEdges. [Answer: The main limitation of the Master Node rewiring method is that it creates a topology bottleneck, since all the information from the original graph needs to pass through a single hub. This can lead to oversquashing, especially in large graphs. Additionally, we argue that some nodes should not be connected because they don't have valuable information to exchange, while this may be the case for nodes with same structural role.]

1.3.2 Minor comments:

Do you relax (1) to obtain (3), or is (3) a consequence of (2)? In other words, do you impose two relaxations (2) and (3), or one relaxation (2) that consequently results in (3)? [Answer: (1) is the matrix form of the definition of Equitable Partition. (2) is a relaxation of the definition of Equitable Partition and (3) is the consequent result in matrix form.]

Line 092, column 2: "satisfy" should be "satisfies"

Line 253, column 1: "error while" should be "error, while"

Equation (5): Is W_s supposed to be W_s^* ? [Answer: W_s^* are the weights obtained when convergence to the global optimum is achieved, while W_s is used to denote the student weights in general. Of course, these two quantities are the same when convergence is achieved, but we prefer to keep the notation W_s in the equations to avoid confusion.] Also, is W_t defined analogously to W_s ? This is not stated explicitly, although I do not find it highly critical to do so. [Answer: Yes, it is defined analogously and it is actually stated explicitly in Equation (5) with the additional definition of $e^{(c)}$.]

I do not believe you defined E_{tot} in the body of the paper, yet it appears after equation (6). [Answer: We thank the reviewer for pointing out this issue. Even if E_{tot} is defined in the Appendix, we will make sure to add it in the body of the paper.]

There ought to be a reference in line 600 on the low-pass behavior of GNNs. I know it is well known, but there have been seminal works that advanced our understanding of this behavior that are worth crediting.

Table 4 caption: "restriced shifts operators" should be "restricted shift operators"

2 Official Review of Submission12905 by Reviewer 5tPe

2.1 Summary:

The authors study the graph rewiring techniques.

By modifying the graph structure, the authors aimed to incorporate information from far-hop neighbors for better downstream task performance.

Through experiments, the authors demonstrate that the proposed method improves node classification performance compared to the original graph setting.

2.2 Strengths And Weaknesses:

2.2.1 Strength

S1) The authors examined their approach under diverse GNN architectures. S2) The authors used various graph datasets for comparison.

2.2.2 Weakness

W1) For me, graph rewiring appears to be a form of graph augmentation, as both aim to modify the graph topology to improve downstream performance. Given this similarity, I believe the authors should also compare the proposed method with existing graph augmentation techniques to better demonstrate its effectiveness. [Answer: We respectfully disagree with the reviewer. While graph rewiring is indeed a part of it, the field of graph augmentation is too vast and diverse to compare any new rewiring technique with it. Indeed, to the best of our knowledge, no paper proposing new graph rewiring techniques does it. In addition to this, not all graph augmentation methods have the same applications. In [1], for example, a very well cited survey, the authors refer only to graph rewiring and graph diffusion as indicated techniques to overcome oversquashing. In the same work, the authors provide a classification of graph augmentation methods based on the applications for which they are intended for. Nevertheless, we could include [1] in our literature review to better position our work with respect to the field of graph augmentation, and we could also add a discussion on how our method is different from other graph augmentation techniques.]

[Additional References: [1] Kaize Ding, Zhe Xu, Hanghang Tong, and Huan Liu. 2022. Data Augmentation for Deep Graph Learning: A Survey. SIGKDD Explor. Newsl. 24, 2 (December 2022), 61–77. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3575637.3575646>

]

W2) I think (C2) and (C5) are somewhat ambiguous. What is "artificial bottleneck" and "principled way"? In similar sense, I cannot understand the authors claim that "Using a ϵ -AEP satisfies (C2) and (C5)." How can we verify this? [Answer: We thank the reviewer for giving us the opportunity to better explain these concepts. The notion of topological bottleneck is well-known in the literature on oversquashing and graph rewiring and by "artificial bottleneck" we intended to indicate a topological bottleneck that is not natively in the graph, but introduced by a particular rewiring method. For example, the Master Node rewiring method creates a bottleneck because all the information from the original graph needs to pass through a single hub.

By "principled way" we mean that the rewiring method (i.e., the creation of virtual nodes and of the edges that connect them to nodes in the original graph) is based on a well-defined and theoretically grounded approach. In the case of RAWR, the virtual nodes are created according to the ϵ -AEP.

This satisfies (C2) because it allows for the creation of multiple virtual nodes that can capture different structural roles, thus avoiding the bottleneck created by a single master node. It also clearly satisfies (C5) because it is based on a clear mathematical framework that defines how many virtual nodes are created and how these are connected to the original graph according to the partition.]

W3) Comparison with existing graph rewiring techniques are missing as well. [Answer: Our proposal is focused on the extension of the Master Node rewiring method, which is a widely used and well-known approach to mitigate oversquashing. In the Literature Review, we report other attempts to produce multiple virtual nodes, but we also show how our approach is the only one, to the best of our knowledge, that satisfy the criteria C1-C5. This is why we compare RAwR with the Master Node rewiring method, which is the most direct baseline.

Nonetheless, we may agree that a wider evaluation on other rewiring techniques could add strength to our work. We report in the Appendix the results of additional experiments we performed thanks to the suggestions of Reviewer f2ws, who pointed us to some well established rewiring methods in the literature.]

2.3 Key Questions For Authors:

Refer to the Weakness section.

3 Official Review of Submission12905 by Reviewer 2hoz

3.1 Summary:

This paper proposes RAwR, a graph rewiring method that introduces multiple role-aware virtual nodes derived from approximate equitable partitions (AEP) of the input graph. Instead of adding a single master node connected to all nodes, the method assigns nodes to structural roles and creates a virtual node per role, enabling role-specific shortcuts for message passing. The rewired graph allows nodes with similar structural roles to communicate within two hops.

3.2 Strengths And Weaknesses:

3.2.1 Strengths:

The proposed rewiring strategy make sense.

The teacher–student analysis provides Some theoretical insight.

3.2.2 Weaknesses:

The paper claims that the proposed rewiring strategy helps mitigate oversquashing and oversmoothing, yet the experimental comparison is incomplete with respect to these claims. Specifically, several widely used baselines designed to address these issues are missing, for example: GCN-II, APPNP, GPRGNN, and even more model-agnostic methods.

The paper focuses exclusively on virtual-node-based rewiring, while a large body of recent work addresses oversquashing through curvature-based rewiring or graph structure learning methods. These approaches are widely studied and represent more mainstream directions for modifying graph topology. However, they are not discussed or compared in the paper. This omission limits the positioning of the proposed method within the broader literature and makes it difficult to assess how it compares with existing topology optimization approaches.

The presentation of the paper could be improved in several aspects: (a)Some motivations are not clearly articulated, particularly why equitable partitions are the most suitable mechanism for defining structural roles. [Answer: In [1] and [2], which are already cited in the paper, the authors motivate the use of equitable partitions for role discovery and they further point to [3]-[6] to further highlight the importance of equitable partitions from a dynamical systems point of view.] (b)Several sections are overly verbose and could be simplified for clarity. [Answer: We thank the reviewer for the suggestion. We will try to further simplify some sections. We kindly ask the reviewer if they could point us to the sections that mostly need to be revised in their opinion.](c)The discussion of related work could better position the method relative to existing rewiring and oversquashing mitigation approaches. Improving the clarity and organization of the writing would make the contribution easier to understand. [Answer: The focus of this proposal is on virtual node rewiring methods and the subsection "Related Work" reports the major works on this topic, while also framing them into a set of criteria to better understand our contribution. See Table 1.]

3.3 Key Questions For Authors:

Have the authors compared the proposed method with established approaches for mitigating oversmoothing and oversquashing, such as GCNII and APPNP, as well as topology optimization methods including curvature-based rewiring and graph structure learning approaches?

[Answer: We thank the reviewer for the question. The goal of our approach is fundamentally different from the suggested methods. GCN-II, APPNP, and GPR-GNN are model architectures specifically designed for mitigating oversmoothing. More in detail, GCN-II introduces initial residual connection and identity mappings to preserve node information across layers, APPNP manages feature propagation through a Personalized PageRank scheme, and GPR-GNN learn adaptive weights for an effective propagation.

In contrast, our approach follows a different philosophy. We do not propose a new GNN model, but a model-agnostic rewiring strategy that operates at the graph level. More in detail, RAWR modifies the topological structure in a principled way to improve the information flow. Due to the complementary nature of our approach, RAWR can be applied to any GNN model, considering the ones mentioned above.

For this reason, the comparison with GCN-II, APPNP, and GPR-GNN is not entirely aligned with the scope of our contribution. Instead, we conduct an extensive analysis considering the standard backbone models.

Additionally, we performed other experiments thanks to the suggestions of Reviewer f2ws, who pointed us to some well established rewiring methods in the literature. We report in the appendix the results, which confirm the superiority of our method.]

Such comparisons would help better understand whether the observed improvements stem from the proposed role-aware rewiring or simply from introducing additional shortcut connections. [Answer: We actually already answered this question on the paper by comparing the performances of GNN architectures on RAWR-rewired graphs against the same architectures on graphs rewired with virtual nodes generated from random partitions (Table 3 in our manuscript): we show that our method consistently outperforms random partitions, reinforcing the idea that RAWR is more than simply adding additional shortcut connections.]

How sensitive is the method to the tolerance parameter ε in practice?

[Answer: The tolerance parameter ε controls the granularity of the roles identified in the network. In general, larger values of the tolerance lead to coarser partitions, resulting in a smaller number of roles. Since ε defines a tolerance over differences in the connections toward equivalent roles, the relationship between increasing ε and the resulting number of roles is not smooth. In practice, small variations in ε often produce identical partitions and, consequently, similar results. Indeed for the setting of the tolerance ε , instead of relying on a fine-grained grid-search, we consider different percentiles of the degree sequence (since ε is connected to the node degrees in each block of the partition, as stated clearly in Equation 2) to explore partitions with different roles. We illustrate in Figure 3 how the choice of the tolerance parameter ε correlates with the SRL and how this metric correlates with the performance of standard backbone architectures.]

What is the computational cost of computing approximate equitable partitions on large graphs?

[Answer: Roles are computed with a polynomial partition refinement algorithm proposed in [1]. The computational complexity of this algorithm is $O(mn)$, where n is the number of nodes and m is the number of edges. This is indeed a worst-case scenario and the authors of [1] showed that, in practice, the algorithm scales efficiently and is able to handle networks with more than 10^5 nodes with short running times.]

[Additional References: [1] Squillace, G., Tribastone, M., Tschaikowski, M., and Vandin, A. Efficient network embedding by approximate equitable partitions. In Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining (ICDM), 2024]

[Answer: [2] Scholkemper, M. and Schaub, M. T. An optimization-based approach to node role discovery in networks: Approximating equitable partitions. In Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), 2023.

- [3] S. Tognazzi, M. Tribastone, M. Tschaikowski, and A. Vandin, “Differential equivalence yields network centrality,” in ISOLA, 2018, pp. 186–201.
- [4] R. J. Sánchez-García. Exploiting symmetry in network analysis. *Communications Physics*, 3(1):1–15, 2020.
- [5] M. T. Schaub, N. O’Clery, Y. N. Billeh, J.-C. Delvenne, R. Lambiotte, and M. Barahona. Graph partitions and cluster synchronization in networks of oscillators. *Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science*, 26(9):094821, 2016.
- [6] Y. Yuan, G.-B. Stan, L. Shi, M. Barahona, and J. Goncalves. Decentralised minimum-time consensus. *Automatica*, 49(5):1227–1235, 2013.]

Would the proposed rewiring still provide improvements when using more expressive GNN architectures?

[Answer: We conduct an extensive analysis considering GCN, GAT, and GIN as representative backbone architectures. Since our method operates at the graph level, it is inherently model-agnostic and can be readily applied to more expressive GNN architectures as well.

Considering that our method improves the underlying graph topology and that the more expressive architectures build upon or extend the standard backbones, we expect our method to transfer naturally to such settings. Therefore, we are confident that similar performance improvements would be observed when applying our approach to more expressive architectures. For further discussion on this topic, we point Reviewer 2hoz to the answer already given to Reviewer Buhs for the comments on Lines 316-317, column 2.]

4 Official Review of Submission12905 by Reviewer f2ws

4.1 Summary:

The authors propose a rewiring method to improve global information diffusion in GNNs. To achieve this, the authors propose incorporating multiple virtual nodes based on the structural role similarity between nodes. Node classification experiments demonstrate that this new graph is better suited to achieve superior performance compared to both the original graphs and the use of a single master node.

4.2 Strengths And Weaknesses:

4.2.1 Strengths

[S1] Taking the structural role of nodes into account represents an interesting and novel direction for rewiring methods.

[S2] The analysis proposed to quantify the structural role makes sense, and investigating its importance seems interesting even beyond rewiring methods.

[S3] The paper is well written and easy to follow.

4.2.2 Weakness

[W1] Novelty position

While connecting nodes with similar structural roles is an interesting idea, the general idea of exchanging information this way is in my opinion not entirely new. [Answer: To the best of our knowledge, no one has ever published a rewiring method based on structural roles/equitable partitions. If the reviewer is indeed aware of such a method, we would be grateful if they could provide a citation.] Additionally, the use of multiple virtual nodes instead of a single master node has been explored before, and I feel the paper could do more to justify why this specific design choice is the best way to capture structural similarity. [Answer: Structural similarity between nodes is captured by the ε -AEP, which finds a partition of the nodes of a graph. Using multiple virtual nodes is our additive rewiring choice that translates the structural roles into virtual hubs. We believe this to be interesting also because the parameter ε allows to find a natural connection to the single virtual node setting.] For instance why use multiple virtual nodes rather than a hypergraph? [Answer: Using hyperedges instead of multiple virtual nodes is interesting and certainly a possibility, but unpractical if we observe existing libraries for graph learning where most implemented features regard graphs and not hypergraphs: here, in fact, we show how RAwR improves the well established backbones of GCN, GIN and GAT. Furthermore, translating roles into multiple virtual nodes allows to define also edges through these roles according to the quotient graph of the ε -AEP, further adapting virtual node embeddings to how roles interact between themselves: this would not be possible with role hyperedges, or it would require to add hyperedge embeddings and a mixing function to combine them with node embeddings (shifting from a model-agnostic rewiring to a specific model architecture).]

How do you position your approach relative to fractal nodes [1]? What are the specific advantages of your method in this regard ?

[1] Are Graph Transformers Necessary? Efficient Long-Range Message Passing with Fractal Nodes in MPNNs, J Choi et al., AAAI 2026

[Answer: We thank the reviewer for the citation of this work. While it would have been impossible for us to compare, in our submitted paper, RAwR to fractal nodes (since [1] has been published in the Proceedings of AAAI 2026 Conference on the 14th May 2026), we take the chance of positioning

our approach against it in this rebuttal. Fractal nodes are defined as virtual nodes which represent blocks of a graph partition: this is indeed very close to RAwR, where we additionally specify that the partition is a ε -AEP. While Total Effective Resistance reduced by adding any type of fractal node, as the authors of [1] show, we argue that still not all types of partitions are useful for the task of node classification. The authors of [1] decided to obtain the partition with the METIS algorithm: this has the effect of capturing some kind of community structure and for this reason, they compare METIS to Louvain and Girvan-Newman. Communities are inherently homophilic (i.e., a community is a set of nodes that is more densely connected within the set than to the outside), while similar structural roles can be found also in long distant nodes. This is why in our proposal we quantify through SRL the effect of the Role-Aware Rewiring on the node classification task, finding also a proxy for the selection of the parameter ε which also decides the number of virtual nodes (this type of pre-training selection is not possible in [1]). Our approach is also model-agnostic in the assignment of edges between virtual nodes (this is the RAwR variant that we call RepEdges), since it is determined by the quotient graph of the ε -AEP. The authors of [1], instead, present no principle to obtain the coarsened graph and need to train a MLP to mix the embeddings of fractal nodes.]

[W2] Mitigation of over-squashing and over-smoothing

I am also not entirely convinced by the claim that this method mitigates oversquashing and over-smoothing. The authors justify this by stating: “RAwR mitigates oversmoothing and oversquashing by propagating information in two hops among nodes with the same role.” In my opinion, additional results are needed to demonstrate that the method actually mitigates these two issues. For instance, to analyze the potential mitigation of oversquashing, it would be interesting to show the extent to which the rewiring method structurally improves long-distance connections between nodes. One possible approach is to demonstrate how much the effective resistance or the commute time decreases after rewiring. [Answer: Virtual Nodes are already known in the literature for reducing commute time and Effective Resistance. In our paper, we cite [15] and [16], and the work provided by the reviewer [1] further confirms the claim. But we agree that providing some empirical results on this matter would strengthen our proposal. We report here our findings:

Dataset	R_{tot}	$R_{r,tot}$
Actor	$2.92 \cdot 10^7$	$2.03 \cdot 10^7$ (-30.54%)
Chameleon	$1.09 \cdot 10^6$	$8.05 \cdot 10^5$ (-26.45%)
Citeseer	$7.30 \cdot 10^6$	$4.21 \cdot 10^6$ (-42.28%)
Cora	$4.96 \cdot 10^6$	$3.16 \cdot 10^6$ (-36.21%)
Cornell	$3.05 \cdot 10^4$	$1.97 \cdot 10^4$ (-35.40%)
PubMed	$3.13 \cdot 10^8$	$2.05 \cdot 10^8$ (-34.42%)
Squirrel	$3.84 \cdot 10^6$	$2.98 \cdot 10^6$ (-22.44%)
Texas	$2.95 \cdot 10^4$	$1.92 \cdot 10^4$ (-34.84%)
Wisconsin	$4.71 \cdot 10^4$	$3.13 \cdot 10^4$ (-33.63%)

Table 1: Total Effective Resistance in observed dataset (R_{tot}) and in RAwR-rewired graphs (with $R_{r,tot}$ average on rewired graphs for values of ε used in evaluation).

We also point the reviewer to the answer already given regarding the comparison with fractal nodes and the effect on Total Effective Resistance.] Additionally, from a model perspective, the authors could analyze how the Jacobian of the model (which calculates the sensitivity between distant nodes) is impacted. Specifically, it would be convincing to show that two long-distance nodes have a greater influence on one another after the rewiring process. [Answer: We thank the

reviewer for the suggestion of analyzing the Jacobian of the models. However, as pointed out also by Reviewer Buhs, the accuracy improvements obtained by GAT+RAwR on heterophilic datasets imply that these datasets require aggregation from multiple hops (i.e. long-distance signal propagation) and GAT is therefore leveraging the attention weights on the newly added edges to virtual nodes. This, in our opinion, is already a strong empirical evidence of the mitigation of oversquashing from a model perspective.]

To demonstrate the mitigation of oversmoothing, providing at least an empirical analysis using Dirichlet energy could help show that the method truly addresses this phenomenon. Furthermore, it is well known that oversmoothing is exacerbated in dense graph substructures. Since the proposed method adds at least N edges [Answer: While it is true that, if n is the number of nodes in the original graph, the RepNodes variant of RAwR adds indeed n edges, but also adds k nodes. The increase of the number of edges must be then thought in comparison to the increase of number of possible edges which goes from $\frac{n(n-1)}{2}$ to $\frac{(n+k)(n+k-1)}{2}$. Therefore the rewired graph does not become catastrophically denser as the reviewer suggests.], it remains unclear what actual impact this edge addition has on oversmoothing. [Answer: We thank the reviewer for pointing this out and giving us the chance to further explain this. Perhaps it is clearer if we say that RAwR both mitigates oversquashing (as shown above) and **prevents** oversmoothing: that is because through RAwR we eliminate the necessity of using too many layers in order to capture relevant signals from long-distance nodes. Whenever nodes are in the same block of the ε -AEP, they are connected through a virtual node and can exchange information in two hops (meaning that the GNNs require only two graph convolution layers, avoiding the risk of oversmoothing). These are the main reason for which we do not believe that an analysis of MAD, MADGap or Dirichlet energy is required and we respectfully ask the reviewer to reconsider their judgment in the light of these facts.

To further prove our point, a comparison between Tables 2 and 6 in our manuscript shows that deeper models actually achieve similar or worse results than the baselines+RAwR at $L = 2$. In addition, if the RepEdges variant is used, long-distance nodes that are in different blocks of the ε -AEP can exchange information in three hops, if they are connected through the quotient graph. This can create improvements in slightly deeper settings, as it is possible to see in Table 7 of our manuscript.]

(Minor) Providing an analysis of the rewiring method’s impact on the underlying graph structure would further contribute to the paper’s clarity. [Answer: We kindly ask the reviewer to clarify what he means by "impact on the underlying graph structure". If the reviewer intended an analysis to show how the node classification task is improved by RAwR (therefore by how the graph topology is changed), Section 4 and Appendix A,B and C are already dedicated to this topic.]

In my opinion is the major drawback of the paper.

[W3] Experimentation of the method

From an experimental standpoint, I find the evidence currently not fully convincing. The experiments are conducted solely on standard homophilic or heterophilic datasets, which are relatively small. Furthermore, the vast majority of these datasets are known to be suboptimal for rigorously evaluating graph learning methods. Specifically, datasets like Texas, Wisconsin, and Cornell are very small and exhibit extremely high performance variance, while Chameleon and Squirrel are known to contain duplicate nodes (as noted in [11], alternative datasets have been proposed for evaluation under heterophily).

Furthermore, it is necessary to include more baselines, particularly other rewiring methods. The current lack of rewiring baselines makes it difficult to properly assess the value of the results (The reported performances appear rather weak compared to the state of the art). Therefore, I strongly believe the authors must compare their approach against references [2-9], which encompass structural

rewiring [2,3,4], recent feature-aware methods [5,6,7], and virtual node techniques [8,9] [Answer: [8] is not a virtual node technique. The reviewer is probably referring to [10], which is actually already reported in our Literature Review. [9] is already commented above.]

[Answer: Our proposal is focused on the extension of the Master Node rewiring method, which is a widely used and well-known approach to mitigate oversquashing. In the Literature Review, we report other attempts to produce multiple virtual nodes, but we also show how our approach is the only one, to the best of our knowledge, that satisfy the criteria C1-C5. This is why we compare RAwR with the Master Node rewiring method, which is the most direct baseline. We also compare with the original graph setting to show the improvement given by the rewiring process. While we believe that this comparison is sufficient to demonstrate the value of our approach, which is fundamentally different from other rewiring methods that do not produce virtual nodes in a principled and model-agnostic way, we may agree that more experiments on other rewiring techniques could better position our work. **We show in the appendix the results of some additional experiments run for this rebuttal**, with a comparison to your proposed methods SDRF [2], FoSR [4], JDR [6] and, additionally, BORF [17] (which is also employed for comparison by the authors of [6]). We highlight that JDR is strictly relevant for settings in which node features are present, but we extended it also for evaluations with no node features. This, in principle, does not require to change the method, since we only need to substitute the node features matrix $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times f}$ (being f the dimension of the feature vector) with an identity matrix I_n . Pragmatically, this leads the JDR algorithm to have a complexity $O(N^3)$ because of the SVD feature denoising (the assumptions leading to $O(N)$ are no longer valid). For this reason, we decided to remove the feature denoising for the bigger datasets Actor, Citeseer, PubMed and Squirrel. **Our method always achieves the best Average Rank.**]

More broadly, in my opinion I find the evaluation to be limited. Heterophilic datasets are fundamentally different from datasets that require long-range interactions, and achieving performance improvements on these datasets does not prove that the method mitigates over-squashing. If the authors' objective is to demonstrate that their method improves global information diffusion, I strongly recommend evaluating it on datasets specifically designed to test long-range interactions [11,12,13,14]. [Answer: We thank the reviewer for the suggested dataset, especially for [11], which could be a precious addition to our evaluation setup. We must, however, note the following:

- While we agree that heterophily and long-range interactions are not equivalent in principle, it is common in the literature to compare graph rewiring techniques that address oversquashing on the datasets Actor, Chameleon, Citeseer, Cora, Cornell, PubMed, Squirrel, Texas and Wisconsin. Among the works cited by the reviewer [2-10], we find that [2],[5],[6],[7] and [8] actually use the same aforementioned datasets. We also highlight that, while [3],[4] and [10] adopt different datasets, they are evaluating their methods on the task of graph classification/regression and not on node classification.
- We know the datasets PascalVOC-SP and COCO in [12] for node classification, but we believe they are actually not suitable for evaluation of long-range interactions. In fact, even if the authors report that the average shortest path and diameter are large, the node classification task is not designed to require long-range interactions: in those datasets, each node is a superpixel, edges connect only adjacent superpixels, node features are local summaries of the region plus its coordinates, and the node label is inherited from the ground-truth pixel at the mean coordinates of that superpixel region. So both the supervision and the graph construction are strongly local in how they are defined. That is why semantic segmentation (which is closely related to superpixel classification) has been approached mainly with Convolutional Neural

Networks [18]. Furthermore, Bechler-Speicher et al. [19] include PascalVOC-SP and COCO in their list of "poor benchmarks" for graph learning, saying "Their graphs encode coarse-resolution images, with rag-boundary edges drawn to connect super-pixels corresponding to segmented regions. However, this modeling choice is not grounded in theoretical or empirical justification".

- [13] and [14] were not yet published at the time of our submission, and we could not evaluate on them. We will certainly consider them for future work.

We respectfully ask the reviewer to reconsider their judgment in the light of these facts.]

[2] Understanding over-squashing and bottlenecks on graphs via curvature, ICLR 2022, Topping et al.

[3] Understanding Oversquashing in GNNs through the Lens of Effective Resistance, ICML 2023, Black et al.

[4] FoSR: First-order spectral rewiring for addressing oversquashing in GNNs, ICLR 2023, Karhadkar et al.

[5] Delaunay Graph: Addressing over-squashing and over-smoothing using Delaunay triangulation, ICML 2024, Attali et al.

[6] Joint Graph Rewiring and Feature Denoising via Spectral Resonance, ICLR 2025, Linkerhägner et al.

[7] GNNs Getting ComFy: Community and Feature Similarity Guided Rewiring, ICLR 2025, Rubio-Madruga et al.

[8] Dynamic Triangulation-Based Graph Rewiring for Graph Neural Networks, CIKM 2025, Attali et al.

[9] Are Graph Transformers Necessary? Efficient Long-Range Message Passing with Fractal Nodes in MPNNs, J Choi et al., AAAI 2026

[10] Probabilistic Graph Rewiring via Virtual Nodes, Neurips 2024, Qian et al.

[11] A critical look at the evaluation of GNNs under heterophily: Are we really making progress?, ICLR 2023 Platanov et al.

[12] Long Range Graph Benchmark. NeurIPS 2022, Dwivedi et al.

[13] Towards Quantifying Long-Range Interactions in Graph Machine Learning: a Large Graph Dataset and a Measurement, ICLR 2026 Liang et al.

[14] Can You Hear Me Now? A Benchmark for Long-Range Graph Propagation, ICLR 2026 Miglior et al.

[Additional References: [15] Southern, J., Di Giovanni, F., Bronstein, M., and Lutzeyer, J. F. Understanding virtual nodes: Oversquashing and node heterogeneity. In International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR), 2025.

[16] Qian, C., Manolache, A., Morris, C., and Niepert, M. Probabilistic graph rewiring via virtual nodes. In Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), 2024. 38th Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS 2024).

[17] Khang Nguyen, Hieu Nong, Vinh Nguyen, Nhat Ho, Stanley Osher, and Tan Nguyen. 2023. Revisiting over-smoothing and over-squashing using ollivier-ricci curvature. In Proceedings of the 40th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML'23), Vol. 202. JMLR.org, Article 1080, 25956–25979.

[18] Long, Jonathan, Evan Shelhamer, and Trevor Darrell. "Fully convolutional networks for semantic segmentation." Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition. 2015.

[19] Bechler-Speicher, Maya, et al. "Position: Graph Learning Will Lose Relevance Due To Poor Benchmarks." Forty-second International Conference on Machine Learning Position Paper Track.]

Appendix: Additional Experiments

Method	Actor	Chameleon	Citeseer	Cora	Cornell	PubMed	Squirrel	Texas	Wisconsin	Avg.Rank
GCN	25.00 ± 0.74	65.02 ± 0.59	<u>75.18 ± 0.59</u>	82.00 ± 0.97	44.44 ± 0.00	86.15 ± 0.04	61.65 ± 0.22	33.33 ± 0.00	52.00 ± 0.00	5.50
GCN+MN	25.16 ± 0.68	66.30 ± 0.84	-	81.70 ± 0.40	47.78 ± 2.87	-	61.17 ± 0.29	34.44 ± 2.34	48.80 ± 1.69	6.22
GCN+BORF	25.63 ± 0.23	66.43 ± 0.70	68.92 ± 0.35	82.96 ± 0.00	45.56 ± 4.16	-	-	36.67 ± 6.67	<u>56.80 ± 2.99</u>	4.67
GCN+FOSR	25.50 ± 0.38	65.99 ± 0.33	68.49 ± 0.24	83.11 ± 0.18	44.44 ± 0.00	82.09 ± 0.06	61.77 ± 0.54	33.33 ± 0.00	55.20 ± 5.88	5.11
GCN+SDRF	25.37 ± 0.44	64.85 ± 0.58	69.04 ± 0.23	83.48 ± 0.18	44.44 ± 0.00	-	61.65 ± 0.31	33.33 ± 0.00	51.20 ± 1.60	5.67
GCN+JDR	29.16 ± 0.11	66.52 ± 1.53	74.52 ± 0.53	83.70 ± 0.41	41.11 ± 2.72	87.02 ± 0.09	53.19 ± 0.67	46.67 ± 2.72	69.60 ± 1.96	<u>3.00</u>
GCN+RepNodes	25.95 ± 0.37	73.83 ± 0.50	75.24 ± 0.37	81.93 ± 0.66	56.67 ± 2.48	<u>86.46 ± 0.22</u>	65.77 ± 0.38	43.33 ± 2.48	56.00 ± 4.00	2.28
GCN+RepEdges	25.68 ± 0.14	71.37 ± 0.31	75.24 ± 0.37	81.93 ± 0.66	50.00 ± 0.00	<u>86.46 ± 0.22</u>	<u>63.46 ± 0.19</u>	38.89 ± 5.56	51.20 ± 3.35	3.22

Table 2: GCN comparison across baselines and augmentations (with node features). Best scores are highlighted in bold and second-best scores are underlined (for each dataset and Avg.Rank).

Method	Actor	Chameleon	Citeseer	Cora	Cornell	PubMed	Squirrel	Texas	Wisconsin	Avg.Rank
GCN	25.45 ± 0.78	67.84 ± 0.93	68.28 ± 0.20	83.48 ± 0.19	44.44 ± 0.00	<u>82.12 ± 0.06</u>	60.85 ± 0.26	33.33 ± 0.00	50.40 ± 2.07	5.17
GCN+MN	25.39 ± 0.90	68.24 ± 0.35	-	83.24 ± 0.32	46.67 ± 2.79	-	60.73 ± 0.53	35.56 ± 2.79	49.60 ± 2.01	5.94
GCN+BORF	25.50 ± 0.92	68.46 ± 0.72	68.55 ± 0.24	83.19 ± 0.18	47.78 ± 2.72	-	-	<u>40.00 ± 6.48</u>	62.40 ± 3.20	4.44
GCN+FOSR	25.82 ± 0.99	68.90 ± 0.72	68.31 ± 0.35	83.26 ± 0.15	44.44 ± 0.00	82.09 ± 0.06	61.19 ± 0.33	33.33 ± 0.00	58.40 ± 1.96	4.39
GCN+SDRF	<u>25.82 ± 0.97</u>	67.93 ± 0.85	68.67 ± 0.33	83.33 ± 0.23	44.44 ± 0.00	-	61.31 ± 0.37	34.44 ± 2.22	52.00 ± 2.53	4.56
GCN+JDR	25.95 ± 0.45	60.18 ± 0.77	69.46 ± 0.45	82.67 ± 0.28	44.44 ± 0.00	82.56 ± 0.12	51.08 ± 0.52	34.44 ± 2.22	50.40 ± 1.96	5.06
GCN+RepNodes	25.39 ± 1.08	75.07 ± 0.23	70.84 ± 0.13	83.33 ± 0.00	55.56 ± 0.00	81.95 ± 0.19	65.42 ± 0.76	43.33 ± 2.34	54.40 ± 2.07	2.50
GCN+RepEdges	25.39 ± 1.08	71.72 ± 0.28	<u>69.79 ± 0.29</u>	<u>83.41 ± 0.16</u>	50.00 ± 0.00	81.93 ± 0.23	<u>63.50 ± 0.72</u>	36.67 ± 4.68	49.60 ± 3.37	<u>3.61</u>

Table 3: GCN comparison across baselines and augmentations (without node features). Best scores are highlighted in bold and second-best scores are underlined (for each dataset and Avg.Rank).

Method	Actor	Chameleon	Citeseer	Cora	Cornell	PubMed	Squirrel	Texas	Wisconsin	Avg.Rank
GAT	25.39 ± 1.02	<u>60.09 ± 5.47</u>	<u>73.25 ± 0.97</u>	81.85 ± 1.59	44.44 ± 3.93	<u>85.43 ± 0.80</u>	42.35 ± 2.82	41.11 ± 3.04	50.40 ± 6.69	<u>3.94</u>
GAT+MN	23.39 ± 1.28	60.00 ± 5.20	-	80.74 ± 0.55	<u>44.44 ± 0.00</u>	-	45.77 ± 0.88	36.67 ± 2.87	48.80 ± 6.75	5.67
GAT+BORF	<u>26.11 ± 0.34</u>	57.53 ± 2.45	60.18 ± 1.05	74.37 ± 2.60	<u>44.44 ± 3.51</u>	-	-	46.67 ± 6.67	52.80 ± 6.88	5.00
GAT+FOSR	24.68 ± 1.28	59.65 ± 2.68	60.66 ± 1.85	74.89 ± 2.45	43.33 ± 2.22	77.13 ± 0.66	<u>45.00 ± 3.61</u>	36.67 ± 6.67	50.40 ± 5.43	5.44
GAT+SDRF	24.53 ± 1.03	59.65 ± 3.84	60.06 ± 1.41	73.41 ± 1.00	42.22 ± 4.44	-	44.96 ± 3.12	36.67 ± 2.72	53.60 ± 8.62	6.17
GAT+JDR	31.08 ± 0.87	50.66 ± 2.77	68.80 ± 0.82	71.70 ± 1.32	41.11 ± 6.67	75.79 ± 0.93	34.50 ± 2.30	<u>42.22 ± 10.30</u>	64.00 ± 3.58	4.89
GAT+RepNodes	25.05 ± 0.80	66.43 ± 3.35	73.61 ± 1.57	82.44 ± 0.89	45.56 ± 2.48	85.46 ± 0.68	45.77 ± 0.93	41.11 ± 6.33	54.40 ± 7.80	2.28
GAT+RepEdges	25.05 ± 0.80	66.43 ± 3.35	73.61 ± 1.57	82.44 ± 0.89	45.56 ± 2.48	85.46 ± 0.68	45.77 ± 0.93	41.11 ± 6.33	54.40 ± 7.80	2.28

Table 4: GAT comparison across baselines and augmentations (with node features). Best scores are highlighted in bold and second-best scores are underlined (for each dataset and Avg.Rank).

Method	Actor	Chameleon	Citeseer	Cora	Cornell	PubMed	Squirrel	Texas	Wisconsin	Avg.Rank
GAT	24.97 ± 0.32	66.34 ± 2.03	61.02 ± 0.74	75.48 ± 1.38	43.33 ± 2.34	<u>77.73 ± 0.91</u>	45.77 ± 2.24	36.67 ± 4.68	51.20 ± 4.92	5.11
GAT+MN	25.29 ± 0.58	67.31 ± 2.11	-	73.85 ± 1.45	44.44 ± 0.00	-	<u>47.62 ± 2.87</u>	36.67 ± 5.81	50.40 ± 4.92	5.22
GAT+BORF	25.47 ± 0.76	<u>67.67 ± 2.62</u>	62.95 ± 1.35	72.67 ± 3.96	42.22 ± 2.72	-	-	36.67 ± 4.44	56.00 ± 6.69	5.00
GAT+FOSR	26.03 ± 0.62	66.26 ± 1.41	<u>61.39 ± 3.14</u>	73.70 ± 4.42	44.44 ± 0.00	76.94 ± 0.94	45.58 ± 1.00	35.56 ± 5.67	55.20 ± 4.66	4.28
GAT+SDRF	25.95 ± 0.68	65.99 ± 1.43	61.02 ± 0.70	73.70 ± 1.42	<u>43.33 ± 2.22</u>	-	45.85 ± 1.25	34.44 ± 2.22	53.60 ± 3.20	5.83
GAT+JDR	25.34 ± 0.41	40.97 ± 2.10	37.53 ± 1.09	46.30 ± 3.39	44.44 ± 0.00	82.43 ± 0.48	51.88 ± 2.33	57.78 ± 2.72	52.00 ± 0.00	4.56
GAT+RepNodes	26.00 ± 0.59	68.81 ± 0.80	61.20 ± 1.67	73.85 ± 1.49	44.44 ± 0.00	76.56 ± 1.01	47.62 ± 2.94	37.78 ± 4.38	56.00 ± 2.67	2.78
GAT+RepEdges	26.00 ± 0.59	68.81 ± 0.80	61.14 ± 1.70	73.85 ± 1.49	44.44 ± 0.00	76.56 ± 1.01	47.62 ± 2.95	37.78 ± 4.38	56.00 ± 2.67	<u>2.89</u>

Table 5: GAT comparison across baselines and augmentations (without node features). Best scores are highlighted in bold and second-best scores are underlined (for each dataset and Avg.Rank).

Method	Actor	Chameleon	Citeseer	Cora	Cornell	PubMed	Squirrel	Texas	Wisconsin	Avg.Rank
GIN	24.39 ± 0.22	61.15 ± 2.56	<u>73.13 ± 1.38</u>	83.04 ± 1.03	51.11 ± 4.65	<u>84.13 ± 0.35</u>	65.23 ± 2.04	58.89 ± 3.04	49.60 ± 6.07	4.44
GIN+MN	24.92 ± 0.69	62.73 ± 3.09	-	82.74 ± 1.12	43.33 ± 2.34	-	<u>65.65 ± 3.58</u>	56.67 ± 4.38	50.40 ± 3.37	5.39
GIN+BORF	24.84 ± 1.40	62.20 ± 1.75	67.83 ± 1.25	80.89 ± 1.94	48.89 ± 5.44	-	-	47.78 ± 2.72	<u>57.60 ± 4.08</u>	5.44
GIN+FOSR	24.34 ± 1.71	<u>63.52 ± 1.40</u>	67.11 ± 0.92	82.30 ± 0.86	44.44 ± 0.00	80.45 ± 0.40	63.38 ± 2.34	40.00 ± 4.16	63.20 ± 2.99	5.11
GIN+SDRF	24.21 ± 1.93	63.44 ± 1.78	66.93 ± 0.44	82.22 ± 0.52	50.00 ± 6.09	-	64.00 ± 0.98	43.33 ± 8.16	55.20 ± 4.66	5.56
GIN+JDR	28.24 ± 1.76	40.97 ± 3.49	67.53 ± 1.05	73.04 ± 1.37	43.33 ± 4.16	79.74 ± 0.52	28.12 ± 3.91	56.67 ± 2.22	53.60 ± 4.80	5.56
GIN+RepNodes	<u>25.66 ± 1.74</u>	71.28 ± 1.57	75.00 ± 0.70	83.93 ± 0.85	54.44 ± 7.24	84.63 ± 0.39	66.81 ± 3.30	61.11 ± 6.80	52.80 ± 1.79	2.00
GIN+RepEdges	25.66 ± 1.74	71.28 ± 1.57	75.00 ± 0.70	83.93 ± 0.85	54.44 ± 7.24	84.63 ± 0.39	65.65 ± 3.80	61.11 ± 6.80	52.80 ± 1.79	<u>2.17</u>

Table 6: GIN comparison across baselines and augmentations (with node features). Best scores are highlighted in bold and second-best scores are underlined (for each dataset and Avg.Rank).

Method	Actor	Chameleon	Citeseer	Cora	Cornell	PubMed	Squirrel	Texas	Wisconsin	Avg.Rank
GIN	24.66 ± 0.96	63.35 ± 0.68	<u>68.67 ± 0.72</u>	82.89 ± 0.80	47.78 ± 5.97	80.43 ± 0.43	64.65 ± 4.07	<u>54.44 ± 2.34</u>	48.00 ± 2.67	5.17
GIN+MN	25.13 ± 0.91	61.94 ± 4.53	-	82.59 ± 0.80	45.56 ± 2.28	-	64.73 ± 3.47	58.89 ± 2.79	49.60 ± 3.28	5.56
GIN+BORF	25.00 ± 0.67	<u>64.32 ± 3.49</u>	68.86 ± 0.86	82.15 ± 1.08	<u>52.22 ± 2.72</u>	-	-	52.22 ± 2.72	60.80 ± 5.88	4.22
GIN+FOSR	24.92 ± 1.40	63.17 ± 5.92	68.07 ± 1.45	81.93 ± 1.00	46.67 ± 2.72	80.07 ± 0.36	<u>65.38 ± 1.71</u>	34.44 ± 2.22	<u>59.20 ± 4.66</u>	5.56
GIN+SDRF	24.92 ± 1.38	63.26 ± 5.17	<u>68.67 ± 0.69</u>	82.96 ± 0.47	48.89 ± 4.16	-	65.35 ± 1.67	47.78 ± 2.72	51.20 ± 2.99	4.72
GIN+JDR	<u>25.03 ± 1.07</u>	52.51 ± 5.13	52.29 ± 0.93	68.37 ± 0.90	48.89 ± 8.89	82.58 ± 0.65	27.73 ± 1.61	46.67 ± 2.72	53.60 ± 3.20	5.50
GIN+RepNodes	25.13 ± 0.93	71.89 ± 2.76	68.55 ± 1.51	82.96 ± 0.65	55.56 ± 0.00	<u>80.49 ± 0.58</u>	67.27 ± 0.94	58.89 ± 2.87	52.00 ± 4.62	2.39
GIN+RepEdges	25.13 ± 0.93	71.89 ± 2.76	68.55 ± 1.51	82.96 ± 0.65	55.56 ± 0.00	<u>80.49 ± 0.58</u>	65.38 ± 2.29	58.89 ± 2.87	52.00 ± 4.62	<u>2.56</u>

Table 7: GIN comparison across baselines and augmentations (without node features). Best scores are highlighted in bold and second-best scores are underlined (for each dataset and Avg.Rank).